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Chemical constituents and cytotoxicity for *Peliosanthes micrantha* rhizomes

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ABSTRACT

The medicinal plant *Peliosanthes micrantha* of Vietnam has been researched recently. This study explored water extracts of ethanol-extracted *P. micrantha* rhizome. *P. micrantha* rhizome was first extracted by ethanol (PM-R-ET). Then, sequential water extract of ethanol-extracted *P. micrantha* rhizome was carried out (PM-R-ET-W), analyzed by Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography-Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (QTOF-MS), and Gel Permeation Chromatography analysis (GPC). Its cytotoxicity was evaluated against five cancer cell lines using MTT assay. In the PM-R-ET-W extract, QTOF-MS tentatively assigned five known compounds, pumilaside A, pumilaside C, β -sitosterol, glycoside J-1, and peliosanthoside B. GPC showed one structurally-unresolved high molecular compound with MW 16.293 Da enriched to 19.3% w/w. PM-R-ET-W cytotoxicity values were moderate against all five MCF-7, Hela, HT-29, HepG2, and A549 cancer cells. The QTOF-MS-identified known compounds in the PM-R-ET-W extract should be later isolated for further biological assays. The GPC-analyzed high molecular compound of 16.293 Da quantified at 19.3 % w/w should be structurally determined. All the tested cell lines' cytotoxicity values of the PM-R-ET-W were moderate. Six identified compounds should be isolated and tested for their cytotoxicity.

Keywords: *Peliosanthes micrantha*, water extract, UHPLC-QTOF, cytotoxicity, cancer cell lines

1. INTRODUCTION

Peliosanthes micrantha Aver. & N.Tanaka, sp. nov. belonging to Asparagaceae in central highland Vietnam is used for detox, body nourishment, and male vitality enhancement [1]. From the ethanol extract of *P. micrantha* rhizomes, Thuy et al. [2] tentatively assigned four compounds, namely, pumilaside A, pumilaside C, glycoside J-3, and β -sitosterol by QTOF-MS analysis. In one unpublished study, they have also isolated two compounds, pumilaside A and β -sitosterol. A sequence extraction by different solvents (e.g., ethanol and then water) might lead to different compositions of constituents. Two chromatographic methods are used to study the chemical constituents of different molecular masses, namely HPLC-QTOF-MS for detecting the secondary metabolites [3] and GPC for determining high molecular weight compounds, distribution, and quantification [4].

Plant-based medicines have potential as a primary source of chemotherapeutic drugs. The first step of developing new antitumor compounds is testing a wide range of natural and synthetic compounds for their cytotoxic effects and then secondly carrying out *in silico* studies. Cytotoxicity can be measured by the most commonly used MTT assay, which is based on the conversion of yellow-colored tetrazolium salt into violet-colored, water-insoluble formazan.

This reduction occurs proportionally, as only living cells have such ability [5]. Many tumor cell lines such as rat brain glioma (C6), normal African green monkey kidney fibroblast (CV1-P), mouse macrophage (RAW264.7), mouse fibroblast (3T6), and human promyelocytic leukemia tumor (HL60), neuroblastoma (SH-SY5Y), including popular human breast adenocarcinoma (MCF-7 and T47D), cervical cancer (HeLa), colon carcinoma (HT29), liver cancer (HepG2), and lung adenocarcinoma (A549) cells have been tested for *in vitro* cytotoxic potential [6]. The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-2), and human caspase-3 proteins are therapeutic targets to develop new generation tyrosine kinase inhibitors against breast cancer cells MCF-7 and T47D [7-10], cervical cancer cells HeLa [11-13], colon carcinoma cells HT29 [14-16], liver cancer cells HepG2 [17-19], and lung adenocarcinoma cells A549 [20-22], respectively.

In this study, *P. micrantha* rhizome was sequentially extracted by water after ethanol extraction. The extract was analyzed by QTOF-MS, and GPC. It was then assessed by FTIR spectroscopy, and finally cytotoxic activities against five human cancer cell lines.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

All reagents, ethanol, anhydrous sodium sulphate, sulphuric acid, glucose, chromatographic-grade standard dextran, HPLC grade acetonitrile, methanol, and analytical grade formic acid ($\geq 98\%$) were obtained from Fisher (USA). L-glutamine, sodium pyruvate, NaHCO_3 , penicillin, streptomycin, Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), Trypsin, EDTA, 3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide (MTT), Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (DMEM), and ellipticine were obtained from Life Technologies, Inc., (Gaithersburg, MD, USA). Tris-base, Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) were obtained from MP Biomedicals (Strasbourg, France). Human breast carcinoma MCF-7 cells, cervical carcinoma HeLa cells, colorectal carcinoma HT-29 cells, hepatocarcinoma HepG2 cells, and lung carcinoma A549 cells, were obtained from Prof. J. M. Pezzuto, Long-Island University (US) and Prof. Jeanette

Maier, University of Milan (Italy).

2. 2. Plant material

The rhizomes of *P. micrantha* were collected in Dak Nong Province, Vietnam in October 2021, and identified by Dr. Nguyen Sinh Khang, Institute of Ecology and Biological Resources, Vietnam Academy of Science and Technology (VAST).

Figure 1. *Peliosanthes micrantha* discovered in Dak Nong province, Vietnam.

The voucher specimen (PM-R) has been lodged at the Center for High Technology Development, VAST. The fresh rhizomes of *P. micrantha* were washed, sliced, dried in an oven at 70 °C, and ground into fine powder using an agate mortar. The dried powder was finally sifted using sieves with mesh sizes ranging between no.100 and no. 120, aimed at isolating particles with dimensions falling within the 0.125-0.150 mm range.

2. 3. Extract preparation

Dried powder of the rhizomes of *P. micrantha* (2.800 kg) was extracted with 95% ethanol (17.5 L × 3 times) at room temperature in an ultrasonic extractor (20 kHz, 1 kW) as described previously giving PM-R-ET extract [2]. After ethanol extraction, the residues were filtered, and dried. The dried powder (2.224 kg) was extracted in one extractor using boiling distilled water (8.96 liters) at 80 °C for 4h and then filtered. Residue extraction was repeated 3 times. The filtrate was concentrated under a reduced vacuum to obtain PM-R-ET-W extract. Both samples were stored at -20 °C for future use.

2. 4. UHPLC-QTOF analysis

Sample analysis by the UHPLC-QTOF instrument was investigated with the procedure described elsewhere [2]. 100.0 mg of PM-R-ET-W was accurately weighed into a tube with a cover, and 2.0 mL methanol-water (8:2, v/v) solvent was added. The sample was ultrasonicated for 10 min, then filtrated through a 0.45 (μm) filter membrane before injecting for analysis. Sample analysis was performed on an ExionLCTM UHPLC system (AB SCIEX, USA) consisting of ExionLC degasser, AC pumps, AC autosampler, controller, and AC column oven. Samples were analyzed on a Hypersil GOLD C18 column (150×2.1 mm, 3μ) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The mobile phase, water containing 0.1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile containing 0.1% formic acid (B), was run at a flow rate of 0.4 (mL/min) at room temperature.

The gradient programming was as follows: 0-4 min, 2-20% B; 4-30 min, 20-68% B; 30-32 min, 68-98% B; 32-40 min, 98% B. Sample injection volume was 5.0 (μL). An X500R QTOF mass spectrometer (AB SCIEX, USA) with a Turbo V ion source was coupled with the UHPLC system. Mass data were acquired in both negative (NEG) and positive (POS) Electrospray Ionization (ESI) modes. The ESI-MS conditions were set as follows: the ion source temperature, 500 °C; curtain gas, 30 psi; nebulizer gas (GS 1), 45 psi; heater gas (GS 2), 45 psi. For the TOF MS scan, the mass range was set at m/z 70–2000. For the TOF MS/MS scan, the mass range was set at m/z 50–1500. For the NEG mode, the ion spray voltage was set at -4.5 kV, the declustering potential (DP) was -70 V, the collision energy (CE) was performed at -20 eV and the collision energy spread (CES) was 10 eV. For the POS mode, the ion spray voltage was set at 5.5 kV, the DP was 80 V, the CE was 20 eV and the CES was 10 eV. All the obtained data were processed by SCIEX OS software version 1.2.0.4122 (AB SCIEX, USA).

2. 5. Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) analysis

2. 5. 1. Qualitative GPC analysis

The molecular weight was determined using GPC analysis with a refractive index (RI) detector and equipped (1.0 mL/min) with a PolySep-GFC P4000 column (300×7.8 mm, Phenomenex). NaNO_3 (0.2 mol/L) and NaH_2PO_4 (0.01 mol/L) were used as the mobile phase [4]. Chromatographic-grade standard dextran with different molecular weights (1, 10, 20, 40, 500, 1000, and 5000 kDa) was used as the standard substance. The MWs of the polysaccharide samples from *P. micrantha* rhizomes were calculated with the help of a calibration curve obtained from dextran standards.

2. 5. 2. Quantitative GPC analysis

Phenol-sulphuric acid method, one of the simple, rapid, precise, and accurate spectroscopic techniques, was modified and optimized to improve repeatability and used for the determination of total polysaccharides in *P. micrantha* rhizomes as described previously with minor modifications [4]. A blank solution was prepared by adding 1 ml of 5% phenol followed by 5 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 to 1 ml of distilled water added.

A series of glucose standard solutions were prepared from a stock solution of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of glucose in distilled water. Aliquots were taken from this solution to obtain sugar concentrations 50-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. 1 ml of 5% phenol solution was added to 1 ml of sugar solution followed by 5 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 . The solution of polysaccharide extracts from *P. micrantha* rhizomes was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of dried polysaccharide extracts in 100 ml of distilled water. From this solution, 1 ml was used for glucose analysis. To estimate the

polysaccharide content in different extracts of *P. micrantha* rhizomes, 1 ml of 5% phenol was added to the 1 ml of polysaccharide solution, followed by 5 ml of concentrated H₂SO₄. The mixture was shaken and incubated at 70 °C for 60 min.

JASCO V 550 UV-VIS Spectrophotometer was employed for all spectroscopic measurements using a pair of matched quartz cells. The absorbance was measured after 10 minutes at 490 nm against blank. The measurement was carried out in triplicate.

2. 6. Cell culture and cytotoxicity assay

MTT assay, as previously described [7], was performed to assess the cytotoxicity of extract of *P. micrantha*. Five carcinoma cells were kept in DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium) or MEME (Minimum Essential Medium with Eagle salt) supplemented with L-glutamine, sodium pyruvate, NaHCO₃, penicillin/streptomycin, 10% FBS (Fetal Bovine Serum), Trypsin-EDTA (0.05%). They were maintained in 25 cm² flasks at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂. The cytotoxic effects of P2 on cancer cells were evaluated by measuring the metabolic activity using the MTT assay. MTT was dissolved in PBS (pH 7.4). The test extract was dissolved in DMSO.

The stock samples were dissolved in DMSO 100% at the concentration of 20 mg/mL. 10 µL of six serial dilutions of test extract (i.e. 0.8, 4.0, 20.0, 100.0, 200.0, and 500.0 ng/µl) were brought in 96-well plates in the culture mediums (without FBS). The cells were grown and regulated to appropriate concentrations, and then 190 µL of the cell medium was brought into the 96-well plates containing 10 µL of test extracts. Ellipticine at different concentrations of 0.4, 2.0, and 10.0 µg/mL was used as a reference. DMSO 10% mL was used as the negative control. The blank negative control without cell and sample were arranged and measured in the well plates of the same test serial. Following incubation for 72 h, the medium was removed, 10 µl MTT (5 mg/ml in PBS) was added to each well, and the cells were incubated for an additional 4 h at 37 °C at 5% CO₂. After 4 h, the supernatant was then removed, and 150 µl DMSO was added to each well. The absorbance at 540 nm was recorded using a BIO-TEK spectrophotometer. The formula used to calculate the inhibition percent (%) was:

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = 100 - \frac{OD(\text{sample}) - OD(\text{blank})}{OD(\text{DMSO}) - OD(\text{blank})} \times 100\%$$

IC₅₀ was calculated by TableCurve 2Dv4 software. Triplicate were repeated.

2. 7. Statistical analysis

Excel (Microsoft Co, Redmond, WA, USA) and SPSS (version 19.0 statistical software, SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) packages were used for statistical analysis. Results represented means ± s.d. of replicated determinations. Comparison and separation of the mean values was performed using Tukey's multiple comparison test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. UHPLC-QTOF MS analysis

The total ion chromatograms (TICs) of PM-R-ET-W in both NEG and POS modes were

shown in Fig. 2. Parent and fragmented ions observed in the mass spectra were summarized in Figs S1 and S2, and Table 1.

Figure 2. TIC of UHPLC-QTOF NEG (a) and POS (b) modes of PM-R-ET-W extract.

Compound **(1)**, at $T_R = 11.48$, in the ESI-QTOF negative mode (Fig. S1), yielded an adduct ion $[M-H]^-$ at m/z 417.1167 (calculated 417.2488), and provided major fragment ions at m/z 239.0711, 251.0699, 255.0626, 268.0718, and 297.0762. It yielded an adduct ion $[M+HCOO]^-$ at m/z 463.1244 (calculated 463.2543), and provided no major fragment ions. The same compound was found *P. micrantha* rhizome earlier and in *Ficus pumila* fruit [2, 23]. Hence, compound **(1)** was tentatively assigned as pumilaside A.

The MS spectra of compound **(2)**, at $T_R = 12.04$, in the ESI-QTOF positive mode (Fig. S2), yielded a parent ion $[M+H-H_2O]^+$ at m/z 383,1814 (calculated). Compound **(2)** was determined as pumilaside C. Kitajima et al. (2000) found pumilaside C in *Ficus pumila* fruit showing the $[M+Na]^+$ ion peak at m/z 423 in the positive FABMS [23].

Compound **(3)** ($T_R = 22.79$ min), exhibited pseudomolecular ion $[M+HCOO]^-$ at m/z 459,1298 (calculated 459,3838), and provided major fragment ions at m/z 297,0761 in the negative mode as shown in Fig. S1. Its ESI-QTOF positive mode spectrum ($T_R = 10.07$ min) showed a sodium adduct molecular ion $[M+Na]^+$ at m/z 437,2375 (calculated 437.3759). Compound **(3)** was assigned as β -sitosterol. Chaturvedula et al. (2012) have isolated β -sitosterol with one molecular ion (M^+) at m/z 414 and several fragment ions at m/z 396, 339, 325, 310, 298, 257, 227, 140, 139, 125, 97, 71, and 57 [24].

Compound **(6)**, at $T_R = 19.64$, in the ESI-QTOF positive mode (Fig. S2), it yielded a parent ion $[M+H]^+$ at m/z 577,1348 (calculated 577.4468), with several fragment ions at m/z 149.0023, 193.0240, 385.0503, and 533.0550. Similar compound, glycoside J-1 from *O. jaburan* spp. was found [25]. Compound **(6)** was tentatively assigned as glycoside J-1.

Compound **(11)**, at $T_R = 11.52$, in the ESI-QTOF negative mode (Fig. S1), yielded a parent ion $[C_{50}H_{78}O_{22}S]^-$ at m/z 1062.7529 (calculated), and provided fragment ion at 1016.7473. Compound peliosanthoside B or glycoside 2 was found with same structure in *P. sinica* [26, 27]. Thus, compound **(11)** was tentatively defined as peliosanthoside B.

Table 1. UHPLC-QTOF assignments of compounds in PM-R-ET-W extract.

T_R (min)	Found mass	Exact mass	Mode	Chemical Name	Formula	MS ion	MS/MS ion
11.48	417.1167	417.2488	NEG	pumilaside A (1)	$C_{21}H_{38}O_8$	$[M-H]^-$	239.0711 251.0699 255.0626 268.0718 297.0762
11.48	463.1244	463.2543				$[M+HCOO]^-$	225.0587 238.0628 239.0706 251.0696 255.0650 268.0729 279.0653 297.0741
12.04	383.1814	437.3759	POS	pumilaside C (2)	$C_{21}H_{36}O_7$	$[M+H-H_2O]^+$	
22.79	459.1298	459.3838	NEG	β -sitosterol (3)	$C_{29}H_{50}O$	$[M+HCOO]^-$	297.0761

10.07	437.2375	437.3759	POS			[M+Na] ⁺	-
19.64	577.1348	577.4468	POS	glycoside J-1 (6)	C ₃₅ H ₆₀ O ₆	[M+H] ⁺	149.0023 193.0240 385.0503 533.0550
11.52	1062.7529		NEG	peliosanthoside B (11)	C ₅₀ H ₇₇ O ₂₂ S	[C ₅₀ H ₇₈ O ₂₂ S] ⁻	1016.7473

From the PM-R-ET-W extract, negative and positive modes of QTOF-MS could identify four known compounds, namely pumilaside A, pumilaside C, β-sitosterol, glycoside J-1, and peliosanthoside B.

3. 2. GPC analysis

The high molecular weight (MW) of the constituent was estimated using high-performance gel permeation chromatography. Each sample was replicated three times. The qualitative GPC analysis data represent the average molecular weight for the entire polymer distribution. Qualitative GPC analysis of PM-R-ET-W extract indicated the presence of a constituent at R_T = 7,633 min with high MW of 16.293 Da (Fig. 2). Using the proposed quantitative GPC method, the calibration equation obtained was found to be $y = 0.0199x + 0.0118$.

A correlation coefficient of 0.991 indicates good linearity between the glucose concentration range between 50-100 μg/ml and absorbance. The high MW constituent content of PM-R-ET-W extract was calculated using a regression equation obtained from the calibration curve and found to be 19.3 % w/w.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3(a,b). a) GPC chromatogram of PM-R-ET-W extract and b) MW of high MW constituent.

3. 3. Cytotoxic activity

The cytotoxic activity of the PM-R-ET-W extract was determined by IC₅₀ value. This IC₅₀ value is the concentration needed to inhibit cell proliferation by 50%. Results of the cytotoxic activity of PM-R-ET-W extract evaluated against five cancer cell lines using MTT assay were shown in Table. 2. The IC₅₀ values of water extract from *P. micrantha* rhizomes against MCF-7, Hela, HT-29, HepG2, and A549 cells were 197.52 ±8.35, 164.62 ±10.14, 90.21 ±5.98, 91.18 ±4.37 and 186.53 ±11.54 µg/mL, respectively.

Table 2. Cytotoxicity values of PM-R-ET-W extract against five carcinoma cells.

Sample		MCF7	Hela	HT29	HepG2	A549
PM-R-ET-W	IC ₅₀ ±SD (µg/mL)	197.52 ±8.35	164.62 ±10.14	90.21 ±5.98	91.18 ±4.37	186.53 ±11.54
Ellipticine		0.39 ±0.02	0.34 ±0.03	0.36 ±0.03	0.32 ±0.02	0.40 ±0.03

Several inhibitors are used to compare the cytotoxic effects of the metabolites. As a positive control for five carcinoma cells, a potent genotoxic agent ellipticine was used [28]. It

yielded IC₅₀ values of 0.39 ±0.02, 0.34 ±0.03, 0.36 ±0.03, 0.32 ±0.02, and 0.40 ±0.03 µg/mL against MCF-7, Hela, HT-29, HepG2, and A549 cells, respectively.

Hanh et al. [29] isolated pumilaside A from the aerial parts of *Artemisia vulgaris* and showed that the compound did not show any significant cytotoxicity on MCF7 and HepG2 cell lines by the SRB assay. However, pumilaside A isolated from Litchi semen exhibited significant in vitro antitumour activity against Hela, Hep-G2, A549, and LAC cell lines with IC₅₀ values of 0.012-6.29 µM by MTT assay. Pumilaside A from Litchi semen has been also proven to induce apoptosis in human gastric cancer BGC823 cells [30].

Previous studies have reported that β-sitosterol had various cytotoxic activities against several cancer cells. Malek et al. [31] reported that β-sitosterol isolated from the *Pereskia bleo* plant had IC₅₀ values against MCF-7 and A549 cells of 72 µg/mL and 78 µg/mL, respectively. β-sitosterol isolated from the *Chisocheton celebicus* plant had similar cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cancer cells with IC₅₀ values of 57 ±3.8 µg/mL [32], and from the *Berberis lyceum* with cytotoxic IC₅₀ value of 140 ±4.21 µM against HepG2 cancer cell [33].

β-sitosterol mediated silver nanoparticles also induced the cytotoxicity in human colon cancer HT-29 cells [34]. β-Sitosterol showed promising anticancer activities for several other cancer lines. Katja et al. [32] reported that β-sitosterol from the *Chisocheton celebicus* had cytotoxic IC₅₀ activity of 12.45 ±0.050 µg/mL against P-388 murine leukaemia cancer cells. Da Silva et al. [35] also reported that β-sitosterol isolated from the *Passiflora mucronata* plant showed cytotoxic activity against K562 cancer cells with an IC₅₀ value of 8.13 µg/mL. The IC₅₀ values are categorized as moderately cytotoxic based on the National Cancer Institute (NCI) cytotoxic categorization. Thus, the isolated compounds have the mild potential to be anticancer inhibitors.

4. CONCLUSION

This research showed the water extract of *P. micrantha* rhizomes containing eleven metabolites, five known compounds newly discovered in *Peliosanthes* spp., all identified by QTOF-MS spectroscopy. One high molecule of 16.293 Da was quantified at 19.3 % w/w by GPC analysis. Its IC₅₀ cytotoxicity against HT29 cells was 96.14 ±6.12 µg/mL. The findings would encourage further *in vivo* tests to verify the pharmaceutical activities of *P. micrantha* rhizomes.

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